

D-NOSES

Distributed Network for Odour Sensing,
Empowerment and Sustainability

Project final video

D7.6

September 2021 (M42)

Deliverable

PROJECT ACRONYM	GRANT AGREEMENT #	PROJECT TITLE
D-NOSES	789315	D-NOSES

DELIVERABLE REFERENCE NUMBER AND TITLE

D7.6
Project final video
Revision: <v1.4>

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Funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union
Grant Agreement No 789315

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

- ✓ **P** **Public**
- C** Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services

Revision History

REVISION	DATE	AUTHOR	ORGANISATION	DESCRIPTION
v1.1	15.09.2021	Lucia Errandonea	IFC	First draft of contents
v1.2	20.09.2021	Elsa Boloix, Martin Balestrini	IFC	Suggestions on section 1 and 2.
v1.3	22.09.2021	Javier Creus and Valeria Righi	IFC	Final revision
v1.4	23.09.2021	Nora Salas Seoane	Ibercivis, Science for Change	Final review
	30.09.2021	Rosa Arias	Ibercivis, Science for Change	Final review

STATEMENT OF ORIGINALITY

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HOW TO CITE THIS REPORT

Errandonea L., Balestrini M., Boloix E., Creus J., Righi V. (2021), Project final video, D-NOSES, H2020-SwafS-23-2017-789315.

Summary

This document presents the three videos created during the D-NOSES project to disseminate and communicate the project goals, methodologies and the actions developed to raise awareness about odour pollution.

This deliverable D7.6 Project Final Video was initially planned as a delivery of one video showing the project's main achievements, to be presented at the end of the project. However, previous experience of project partner IFC in producing the [documentary](#) for the [EU project Making Sense](#), suggested that producing visual testimonies over the course of the project is instrumental for supporting dissemination and communication activities and increasing awareness over the project. Based on this insight, the consortium decided to split the D-NOSES video into three different pieces to showcase odour pollution issues in different affected communities and the methodologies followed within this innovative methodology using the citizen science approach.

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About the videos

In this chapter we outline the audiovisual production of the D-NOSES project.

The D-NOSES videos include three audiovisual pieces that have been designed for distribution on social media and the project website. The table below presents the main characteristics of each video and the impact reached in terms of number of views.

Title video	Description	Views <i>accessed on the 22 Sept. 2021</i>	Languages	Link
D-NOSES Institutional	Short video explaining the key points about the project: what is D-NOSES, the problem addressed, the methodology used, the expected outcomes and objectives.	1367 (released on March 2019)	Subtitles in: English, Spanish, Italian and German	<p><i>Main Version</i></p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RbS7Ga7pBEU</p> <p><i>Short version (1')</i></p> <p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BTmGlyye6oE</p>
Barcelona Pilot Case	A narrative video about the experience of the Barcelona Pilot	120 (released on April 2021)	English and Spanish	<p><i>Main Version</i></p> <p>English version</p> <p>Spanish version</p> <p><i>Other versions for events</i></p>

				https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UDT7N4Ad2z0
D-NOSES achievements	A summary video to present the impact and achievements of the project.	20 (released on September 20th)	English	https://youtu.be/i-nBqWhTRFU

The three videos were published in the project’s YouTube channel and disseminated through its corresponding social media accounts by the communication leader (ISWA). They have also been published in the social media accounts of the consortium members. Finally, the videos have been showcased in several events, following adaptations of its content (see Chapter 3).

1. D-NOSES institutional video

The [D-NOSES institutional video](#) was launched in March 2019 with the aim to present the project and its goals. The piece stressed how the project included citizen science processes in the odour monitoring and facilitated a quadruple helix involvement for the better management of odour issues. The objective was to stand out that odour pollution is a real problem for communities. The video uses an institutional tone to address the targeted audiences, which are odour experts, other EU initiatives, policy makers and regulators and European public and civic sectors.

Fig 1: Screenshots of the D-NOSES institutional video

Over the course of the production process, many partners participated in the realisation of the video with interviews and footage from the activities developed at the pilot locations.

Regarding technical aspects, the video has a duration of 3 minutes. A shorter version (1 min) has been produced for its distribution in social media accounts ([see here](#)), intended to catch the audience's attention. To increase its outreach, the video has been subtitled in four languages (English, Spanish, Italian and German), and has been showcased in different events such as **European Clean Air Day**¹ or the **ECSA Conference 2020**².

Fig 2: The D-NOSES institutional video in the official website

¹ <https://cleanairday.eu>

² <https://www.ecsa-conference.eu>

2. Barcelona Pilot Case video

The [Barcelona Pilot Case video](#) documents the process implemented across the project pilot in Barcelona. It presents: the issue addressed in the Forum area, how the affected communities are dealing with the odour pollution problem and a step-by-step explanation of the D-NOSES methodology implemented in this pilot location. Finally, the video shows the testimony of four representatives of the Forum community and two interviews to the D-NOSES team from Ibercivis and Ideas for Change, the pilot leaders.

This video has two folded goals: 1) to be an example of the methodology implemented in the different D-NOSES pilots using citizen science to tackle odour issues and 2) to provide the community from the Forum area with an audiovisual material that celebrates their participation. For that reason, the video was launched in the final event³ of the Barcelona pilot. It went online with the community in April 2021.

The duration of the video is 12 minutes, and is available with [English](#) and [Spanish](#) subtitles. The piece is addressed to local authorities and communities, citizen science experts, and other EU initiatives related to the research field.

Fig 3: Screenshot from the D-NOSES Barcelona pilot - Spanish version

³ <https://twitter.com/Ideas4Change/status/1387717067244281861>

Fig 4: Screenshots from the D-NOSES Barcelona pilot - English version

3. D-NOSES achievements video

The [Final video](#) is a compilation of the outcomes and results of the project. It summarizes the methodology of the project, the lessons learned across the 10 pilots, the advocacy actions implemented to bring odour pollution in the policy agenda, and the resources developed to build the legacy of the project

Fig 5: Screenshots of the D-NOSES final video

Fig 6: Screenshots of D-NOSES final video related with the legacy of the project

All the messages that appear on the video were co-defined with the partners. The video, launched on September 21th 2021, has a duration of 3:17 minutes and it was disseminated across the project's social media accounts. The targeted audience is the citizen science community, policy makers and regulators and EU similar initiatives.

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Examples of video adaptations

The videos have been showcased in several events. In order to maximize the reach of the videos and meet the events' requirements, the duration and footage of some specific pieces was adapted. Some examples of adapted versions of the videos are presented below.

3rd Annual Citizen Engagement and Deliberative Democracy Festival ⁴

Adaptation of the Barcelona pilot video for the 3rd Annual Citizen Engagement and Deliberative Democracy Festival organized by the European Commission (December 2020).

The video was shortened to have a duration of 3 minutes. It received 120 views.

- Link to the adapted version here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UDT7N4Ad2z0>

Fig 7: Screenshot of Festival's announcement in the EU Science Hub Portal (left) and Screenshot of the adapted video (right)

Research and Innovation Top Stories - European Commission

The D-NOSES project was selected by the European Commission's DG RTD for being part of the European Commission Political Priorities' videos⁵. The footage of the two first videos as well as inedit material, were sent to the DG.

The final video was entitled: *EU research and innovation is finding new ways to nurture our European democracy*. It received over 40.000 visualisations.

- Link to the video adaptation here:
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QHUn92-IA1E&list=RDCMUC1lhGQ0C_OOlaS1rbxIXM5Q&index=2

Fig 8: Screenshot of the *EU research and innovation is finding new ways to nurture our European democracy* video where D-NOSES was mentioned

⁵ <https://www.research-innovation-exhibition.eu/en/gallery>

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Final remarks

First of all, D-NOSES went beyond its audiovisual material commitment with the creation of 3 videos instead of one final video at the end of the project. The first video wanted to present the purpose of the project to tackle odour pollution using citizen science and participatory strategies developing 10 pilot case studies in Europe and beyond with this innovative methodology. The second one, focused on the affected communities in the Barcelona Pilot, the pioneer pilot case study to tackle odour pollution in Spain and how they were mobilized to gather data in order to better understand the odour issues occurring in the area. The third video shows all results and actions thanks to the development of the project within its 3 years duration.

As a final remark, the audiovisual materials created for D-NOSES supported the project in several ways:

1. To raise awareness about odour pollution as an issue that affects communities all over the world;
2. To support the advocacy and pilot actions as a communication asset;
3. To disseminate the aims, the methodology and the results of the project.

All these materials will remain as a legacy in the [OdourObservatory](#) for future consultation.

Finally, it is considered as a big achievement that the D-NOSES Project has been selected to be showcased at the video from the European Commission *EU research and innovation is finding new ways to nurture our European democracy* as one of the top stories of R&I.

All the D-NOSES Consortium is really proud!